

PREDICTING TEACHERS' BEHAVIORAL INTENTION TO INTEGRATE AI IN EDUCATION: A STUDY OF KEY INFLUENCING VARIABLES

Allan Deanmacgy S. Cruz

*Centro Escolar University, Philippines
Senior High School Department, National University, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15762217>

ABSTRACT

In the Philippines, understanding how teachers perceive the usefulness of AI in education remains critical, as skepticism and ethical concerns continue to hinder its adoption. Many teachers express apprehension about using AI tools due to technological barriers, lack of regulatory policies, and resistance to change. Thus, it is important to understand predictors of behavioral intention to address these challenges, as it provides insights into the factors that motivate or discourage teachers from integrating AI into their practices. This study aims to explore private school teachers' willingness to adopt AI in their teaching practices and identify the factors contributing to its effective integration, using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling. A total of 129 private school teachers from Caloocan and Quezon City who participated in this study. The result shows that perceived usefulness, computer self-efficacy, and social influence significantly influence behavioral intention of teachers to integrate AI. It also highlights the critical role of computer self-efficacy in shaping perceived usefulness, while perceived ease of use was found to have minimal relevance to this context. Findings calls for policymakers, educational institutions, and stakeholders to focus on promoting practical benefits of AI, building teacher confidence, and designing seminar and workshops that emphasize real-world applications and best practices.

Keywords: *AI in Education, Behavioral Intention, Perceived Usefulness, Computer Self-efficacy, Teacher Technology Adoption*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into educational settings has garnered significant attention as it revolutionized various sectors like education. AI technologies are viewed as supplementary tools as it offers a range of tools and applications that can improve both instructional practices and learning outcomes. Teachers and students recognized the ability of AI to make school tasks easier. Teachers can quickly ask AI to draft letters and proposal, improve lesson plans, and adjust activities to match their students' needs. Likewise, students can leverage AI to explain difficult words, create practice questions, and prepare better for their tests, making learning more personalized.

In the Philippines, initiatives to integrate AI into the curriculum have been introduced, but teachers remain divided. While some recognize its benefits in improving teaching and learning, many are concerned about challenges such as ethics, reliability, and the need for proper training. One major concern is the unethical use of generative AI. Teachers use AI technologies for lesson planning, creating materials, and assessments, but they struggle with citing sources since AI-generated content lacks clear attribution. Additionally, students rely on generative AI to complete their homework and activities, making it difficult for teachers to foster creativity and critical thinking, and address cheating and data fabrication (Giray, 2024). Furthermore, teachers express apprehensions about the changing nature of their roles in the classroom. With AI technologies, students can easily access information and interact with AI chatbots to generate ideas that aid their understanding of concepts. However, this increased reliance on AI may reduce students' dependence on teachers as primary sources of knowledge. Lastly, teachers remain apprehensive about AI technologies due to the extra time and commitment required to learn them. This concern is further intensified by the lack of sufficient professional development opportunities and technological barriers, such as limited infrastructure (Sevillano, 2024) and the lack of user-friendly AI tools, particularly affect less tech-savvy educators (Arguson et al., 2023). Hence, teachers' intention to integrate AI is hindered by ethical concerns, lack of institutional support, insufficient training, and technological limitations, emphasizing the need to explore key influences that shape their confidence in AI and their willingness to adopt it in education.

With the aforementioned scenario, the need to explore private school teachers' willingness to adopt AI in their teaching practices and identify the factors contributing to its effective integration, using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). Factors such as teachers' perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, computer self-efficacy, and social influence in integrating technology are considered vital to understanding how teachers perceived and act upon the use of AI tools in education. The study will contribute to the growing body of knowledge on AI in education, providing valuable insights into the barriers and enablers of AI integration. By exploring these variables, the study will provide a clearer understanding of contextual factors that shape teachers' decisions, which can inform educational policy, teacher training, and curriculum development aimed at enhancing AI integration.

Computer Self-efficacy

Computer self-efficacy (CSE) refers to how individuals perceive their ability to use technology. It encompasses confidence in performing both basic and advanced computer operations, as well as utilizing technology for instructional purposes. CSE is categorized into three key factors: self-efficacy in basic operational skills, advanced operational and collaborative skills, and in using computers for teaching (Scherer & Siddiq, 2015).

Empirical evidence supports the predictive power of CSE on technology acceptance. For instance, computer self-efficacy has been shown to predict both perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use of technology (Usman et al., 2020). Similarly, faculty members with higher CSE were more likely to intend to use technology for online teaching, with CSE significantly influencing perceived ease of use (Zhao & Zhao, 2021). Likewise, confident teachers are more likely to see technology as a valuable tool for diverse classroom needs, with higher CSE leading to increased perceived usefulness and enhanced perceived ease of use due to their trust in their capabilities (Yang et al., 2024).

Further research highlights the role of CSE in the context of AI adoption. IT proficiency, a component of CSE, significantly affects teachers' behavioral intentions, with higher self-efficacy increasing their willingness to integrate AI-generated content (Li & Zhang, 2024). Self-efficacy in learning AI directly influences behavioral intentions to learn AI, as teachers' confidence in their ability to understand and use AI tools predicts their likelihood of adoption (Du et al., 2024). However, limited resource access and insufficient professional development can hinder CSE, reducing teachers' confidence and readiness to adopt AI (Alshorman, 2024).

Moreover, self-efficacy is a critical factor influencing overall technology adoption, as it reflects the belief in one's ability to perform tasks using the technology (Marikyan & Papagiannidis, 2023). High AI self-efficacy among educators is often associated with a greater likelihood of successfully adopting and integrating AI in educational practices (Fabella & Sumandal, 2023). On the contrary, low AI self-efficacy is linked to hesitancy and reluctance to engage with AI in teaching (Rajapakse et al., 2024). Teachers' computer self-efficacy has also been shown to positively impact their behavioral intentions to use AI, indicating that higher confidence in technology use enhances the likelihood of adoption (Pelaez et al., 2022).

Based on these readings, the hypotheses are proposed:

H₁: Computer self-efficacy significantly predicts behavioral intention to integrate AI.

H₂: Computer self-efficacy significantly predicts perceived usefulness.

Perceived Ease of Use

Perceived ease of use refers to the degree to which an individual believes that using a technology will require minimal effort. It is a key factor in technology adoption, as

it directly influences users' behavioral intentions to integrate the technology into their practices, according to the TAM (Marikyan & Papagiannidis, 2023). This concept aligns with the effort expectancy construct in the UTAUT, which suggests that technologies perceived as easy to use are more likely to be adopted (Li & Zhang, 2024).

Empirical evidence supports this relationship, indicating that when teachers perceive AI as user-friendly, their intention to integrate it into lesson planning increases significantly (Zhang et al., 2023; Acquah et al., 2024; Yao & Wang, 2024). Similarly, perceived ease of use directly enhances teachers' willingness to adopt artificial intelligence-generated content (AIGC) technologies (Lu et al., 2024). Additionally, effort expectancy has been found to influence teachers' behavioral intention to use AI tools (Xiaohong et al., 2024). This underscores the critical role of ease of use in predicting behavioral intention (Nja et al., 2023).

However, some studies suggest that perceived ease of use may not always have a significant direct effect on behavioral intention, especially when teachers already recognize the strong practical benefits of the technology (Wang et al., 2024; Alasgarova et al., 2024). This implies that ease of use might indirectly influence behavioral intention by enhancing perceived usefulness rather than acting as a primary predictor. For instance, in the context of information and communication technology (ICT) integration, teachers who find the technology easy to use are more likely to perceive it as useful, suggesting that ease of use enhances the perceived usefulness of the technology (Usman et al., 2020; Arthur, 2022; Ibrahim & Shiring, 2022).

To ascertain these insights, the hypotheses are proposed:

H₃: Perceived ease of use significantly predicts perceived usefulness.

H₄: Perceived ease of use significantly predicts behavioral intention to integrate AI.

Perceived Usefulness

Perceived usefulness refers to the belief that using a particular technology will enhance one's performance, particularly in educational contexts (Marikyan & Papagiannidis, 2023). This perception is a crucial factor in determining technology adoption. The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) emphasizes the importance of performance expectancy, a concept closely related to perceived usefulness, as a strong predictor of behavioral intention (Li & Zhang, 2024). Similarly, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) highlights perceived usefulness, directly linking it to the likelihood of adopting new technology (Marikyan & Papagiannidis, 2023).

Empirical evidence further stresses the critical role of perceived usefulness in shaping adoption intentions. Studies have shown a strong positive relationship between perceived usefulness and teachers' intention to integrate AI, indicating that educators are more likely to use AI if they believe it enhances teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes (Zhang et al., 2023; Lu et al., 2024; Yao & Wang, 2024). This finding is consistent across different groups, including in-service teachers (Arthur, 2022; Acquah

et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2024) and pre-service teachers (Adelana et al., 2024), who recognize the practical benefits of technology in improving educational practices.

Moreover, studies by Alasgarova et al. (2024) and Du et al. (2024) suggest that perceived usefulness also extends beyond individual benefits. When technology is seen as contributing to broader societal impacts, such as AI for social good, educators are more motivated to learn and adopt it, further reinforcing its significance in driving behavioral intention.

Based on these readings, the hypothesis is proposed:

H₅: Perceived usefulness significantly predicts behavioral intention to integrate AI.

Social Influence

Social influence is defined as the degree to which an individual perceives those important others, such as colleagues, students, or administrators, believe they should engage in a particular behavior (Venkatesh et al., 2003). In educational settings, social influence involves the impact of colleagues' expectations, institutional norms, and prevailing trends on a teacher's decision to adopt innovations such as artificial intelligence (AI) tools in their teaching practices. This concept aligns with subjective norms, emphasizing the pressure or encouragement educators may feel from their professional network to engage in technology integration (Marikyan & Papagiannidis, 2023).

Previous research has highlighted the significance of social influence as a key predictor of technology adoption among teachers. Pre-service teachers, for instance, may feel encouraged or pressured by their peers, mentors, or the educational environment to adopt AI in their instructional practices (Acquah et al., 2024). Additionally, the broader educational community's expectations, including those of administrators, have been shown to influence teachers' intentions to use AI (Wang et al., 2024). Teachers may also be motivated to integrate AI if they believe their colleagues are adopting these tools, creating a normative push to align with peer behavior (Li & Zhang, 2024; Xiaohong et al., 2024). The expectations from students, who increasingly anticipate the use of advanced technologies in their learning experiences, further contribute to this social pressure (Adelana et al., 2024).

Institutional support and encouragement from school leaders, such as department heads and coordinators, play a crucial role in reinforcing teachers' perceptions of the necessity to integrate AI into classroom activities (Alasgarova et al., 2024). Moreover, educational trends advocating for the incorporation of AI in teaching practices may serve as an additional external pressure, aligning with broader shifts in the field of education (Wang et al., 2024). In addition, teachers' behavioral intention to integrate AI is significantly influenced by external, organizational factors such as resources, time, and recognition (Gupta & Baskar, 2020).

Based on this evidence, it is clear that teachers' behavioral intentions are shaped by their perceptions of social expectations, peer norms, and the broader educational environment. Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H₆: Social influence significantly predicts behavioral intention to integrate AI.

Proposed Structural Equation Model

Based on the readings, the researcher proposed a partial least squares structural equation model involving exogenous latent variables which are computer self-efficacy (CS), social influence (SI), and perceived ease of use (PEU), and endogenous latent variables which are behavioral intention to integrate AI (BI), and perceived usefulness (PU). It has two sub-models (see Figures 1 and 2).

Figure 1: Hypothesized Model for Latent Variables

In figure 1, this is the proposed hypothesized or measurement model (outer model) for the latent variables. This specifies the relation between the latent variables and their observed variables. Also, this was used to examine the validity and reliability of each construct contained in the questionnaire.

Figure 2: Structural Model for Latent Variables

On the other hand, Figure 2 is the structural model (inner model) for the latent variables. It shows the relationship between the exogenous and endogenous variables. Then, the significance and strength of the hypothesized relationships between these latent variables in this model will be tested.

Research Questions

This study seeks to explore the factors that influence private school teachers' willingness to adopt artificial intelligence (AI) in their teaching practices. As AI becomes increasingly integrated into educational settings, understanding the determinants of its acceptance and use by educators is essential for effective implementation. The study specifically focuses on constructs such as perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, computer self-efficacy, and social influence, drawing on established technology adoption theories. Using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), the study aims to uncover the relationships among these variables and their impact on teachers' behavioral intention to integrate AI tools.

To guide the investigation, the following research questions were formulated:

1. What factors significantly influence private school teachers' willingness to adopt AI in their teaching practices?
2. How do perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, computer self-efficacy, and social influence collectively and individually affect teachers' willingness to integrate AI into their instructional practices?
3. What are the direct and indirect relationships among these factors in predicting teachers' willingness to adopt AI, as analyzed through PLS-SEM?

METHODOLOGY

This study aimed to explore their willingness of private school teachers from Caloocan and Quezon City to adopt AI in their schools and identify the factors contributing to its effective implementation. Specifically, the study examined whether a relationship exists between teacher's behavioral intention to integrate AI and various factors, determined if these factors can predict their intention to adopt AI in education, and develop a model that explains and predicts the relationships. The factors considered include perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, computer self-efficacy, and social influence.

Sample of the Study

The researcher utilized G*Power, a statistical software, to calculate the necessary sample size for the study with multiple predictors. Using a model with four predictors, an effect size of 0.15, a power level of 0.95, and a significance level of 0.05, the minimum required number of participants was determined to be 129. Therefore, the sample size for this study consists of 129. The demographic profile of the respondents is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents

Variable	Subscale	Frequency	Percentages
Years of Experience	1-4	52	40.3
	5-8	58	45.0
	More than 8	19	14.7
Specialization	STEM Disciplines	45	34.9
	Non-STEM Disciplines	74	57.4
	Early Education	10	7.7

Table 1 reveals that a plurality of the respondents has 5 to 8 years of teaching experience. In addition, majority of the respondents' specialization falls under non-STEM disciplines. The result in table 1 reflects a younger teaching workforce with concentration in non-STEM disciplines.

Construction and Validation of the Instrument

The researcher started by reading related studies to gather vital ideas and data relative to the behavioral intention of teachers to integrate AI in education. Based on these related studies, the researcher identified the latent constructs, including behavioral intention to integrate AI, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, computer self-efficacy, and social influence. Also, specific indicators for each construct were crafted. Then, the researcher asked three academic experts to validate the questionnaire.

The revised instrument was then subjected to pilot testing with a sample of 30 respondents to further assess its reliability and validity. During this phase, indicators with outer loadings below 0.60 were removed to improve the overall measurement quality of the instrument (Ayanwale et al., 2022). Additionally, the reliability and validity of the constructs were assessed using composite reliability (CR) with a recommend threshold of 0.70, average variance extracted (AVE) with an acceptable threshold of 0.50, and Cronbach's alpha which should be greater than or equal to 0.70 (Cheung et al., 2024).

From the initial draft of the questionnaire consisted of five latent variables with a total of twenty indicators, using a 4-point rating scale ranging from 1 (Very Low Extent) to 4 (Very High Extent), and after undergoing validation by academic experts and pilot testing, the final version of the questionnaire was refined to include 17 indicators across the five latent variables. These are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Rating Scale Items of the Study

Code	Item
B11	1. I intend to actively incorporate AI tools in my teaching practices.
B12	2. I plan to use AI technologies in my classroom activities as often as possible.
B13	3. I will prioritize integrating AI-based solutions to enhance my students' learning experience.
B14	4. I see myself adopting AI tools as a regular part of my teaching job.

CS1	5. I am confident in my ability to troubleshoot AI-related problems that occur during class.
CS2	6. I think I can integrate AI into my teaching, even if it requires some learning.
CS3	7. I am comfortable with the idea of using AI technologies to complement my teaching.
PEU1	8. I find AI tools easy to understand and implement in my classroom.
PEU2	9. I believe I can quickly learn how to use AI technologies in my teaching.
PEU3	10. I feel that integrating AI into my teaching will not be a complicated process.
PU1	11. I believe AI can significantly improve the efficiency of my teaching tasks.
PU2	12. I feel that using AI in my classroom will enhance my students' learning outcomes.
PU3	13. I think AI can help me tailor my instructional methods to meet diverse student needs.
PU4	14. I see AI as a tool that can help me achieve my teaching objectives more effectively.
SI1	15. I believe that my colleagues expect me to incorporate AI into my teaching.
SI2	16. I feel that heads and/or coordinators encourage the integration of AI into classroom activities.
SI3	17. I am influenced by educational trends that advocate for AI use in teaching.

Data Collection

The researcher utilized Microsoft Forms to create an online survey, which was then distributed to teachers known to the researcher who reside in Caloocan and Quezon City. Additionally, the researcher requested colleagues to help recruit other private school teachers they knew, encouraging them to voluntarily complete survey. The online survey remained open for nearly four weeks, from November 16 to December 9, 2024, before being closed for data collection.

Data Analysis

With Smart PLS software, version 4.1.0.9, the study utilized Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) to analyze the data collected through the research tool. The software provided assessments for both the measurement model and the structural model. For the measurement model, the evaluations included outer loadings, Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, average variance extracted (AVE), variance inflation factor (VIF) for outer model, Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratios, and the Fornell-Larcker criterion. For the structural model, the assessments covered VIF for inner model, standardized path coefficients, t-values, p-values, and Cohen's effect size (f^2). It also creates a summary of results of the assessments.

RESULTS

Measurement Model Analysis

Table 3. Construct Validity and Reliability

Construct	Items	Loadings	CA	CR	AVE	VIF _{OM}
Behavioral Intention (BI)	BI1	0.872	0.878	0.917	0.734	2.404
	BI2	0.889				2.660
	BI3	0.863				2.424
	BI4	0.800				1.818
Computer Self-efficacy (CS)	CS1	0.810	0.810	0.887	0.723	1.670
	CS2	0.859				1.843
	CS3	0.881				1.825
Perceived Ease of Use (PEU)	PEU1	0.891	0.806	0.886	0.721	2.037
	PEU2	0.859				1.875
	PEU3	0.795				1.552
Perceived Usefulness (PU)	PU1	0.885	0.910	0.937	0.787	2.734
	PU2	0.864				2.311
	PU3	0.891				3.128
	PU4	0.908				3.338
Social Influence (SI)	SI1	0.821	0.781	0.872	0.694	1.691
	SI2	0.851				1.836
	SI3	0.827				1.474

In table 3, it presents the construct validity and reliability of the measurement model. The outer loadings of each indicator (≥ 0.60), Cronbach's alpha (≥ 0.70), composite reliability (≥ 0.70), and average variance extracted (≥ 0.50) of each construct were tested. The measurement model retained all 17 indicators with outer loadings ranging from 0.795 to 0.908. In addition, based on Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability estimates, all constructs measured over 0.70 ranging from 0.781 to 0.910 and 0.872 to 0.937 respectively. Also, all AVE exceeds the value 0.50. The VIF for outer model was also tested to assess the potential issue of multicollinearity among the indicators that are used to measure the latent constructs. The values of VIF for each indicator should be below the threshold of 5 (Hair et al., 2022). The VIF values range from 1.474 to 3.338, and none of these exceed 5. This shows that the indicators in the measurement model do not suffer from significant multicollinearity. Overall, with a satisfactory outer loading, Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, and AVE estimates, together with acceptable VIF values for the outer model, the measurement model demonstrates adequate reliability, validity, and absence of significant multicollinearity.

Table 4. Heterotrait-monotrait Ratios of the Construct in the Model

	BI	CS	PEU	PU	SI
BI					
CS	0.800				
PEU	0.771	0.869			

PU	0.845	0.792	0.771	
SI	0.773	0.661	0.624	0.686

Table 4 displays the discriminant validity of the constructs, using HTMT ratio of correlations. As a criterion for assessing discriminant validity, HTMT values should be less than or equal to 0.90 (Henseler et al., 2015). All constructs in the model recorded HTMT ratios below the threshold of 0.90.

Table 5. Fornell-Larcker Criterion of the Construct in the Model

	BI	CS	PEU	PU	SI
BI	0.857				
CS	0.684	0.850			
PEU	0.655	0.701	0.849		
PU	0.758	0.690	0.661	0.887	
SI	0.646	0.544	0.501	0.588	0.833

Table 5 supports the HTMT ratios of the construct of the outer model. The square root of the AVE (diagonal values) of each construct should be higher than the construct's highest correlation (off-diagonal values) with any other construct in the model (Hair et al., 2022). The square roots of the AVE for each reflective constructs BI (0.857), CS (0.850), PEU (0.849), PU (0.887), and SI (0.833) are all higher than the correlations of these constructs with other latent variables, hence indicating all constructs are valid measures of unique concepts. Based on the evidence provided by Tables 4 and 5, it can be concluded that the constructs in the model demonstrate discriminant validity. Overall, the convergent and discriminant validity assessments revealed constructs in the model to be valid.

Structural Model Analysis

Table 6. Variance Inflation Factor Values in the Structural Model

Path	VIF
Computer Self-efficacy (CS) → Behavioral Intention (BI)	2.469
Computer Self-efficacy (CS) → Perceived Usefulness (PU)	1.965
Perceived Ease of Use (PEU) → Behavioral Intention (BI)	2.249
Perceived Ease of Use (PEU) → Perceived Usefulness (PU)	1.965
Perceived Usefulness (PU) → Behavioral Intention (BI)	2.388
Social Influence (SI) → Behavioral Intention (BI)	1.632

In Table 6, it presents the variance inflation factor values of the inner model to check multicollinearity issues among all combinations of endogenous and corresponding exogenous latent variables. VIF values of all sets of predictor constructs in the inner model should be below 5, which is an acceptable threshold for PLS-SEM (Hair et al., 2022). Since all VIFs measured below range from 1.632 to 2.469, it indicates that there are no multicollinearity issues in the inner model.

Table 7. R-square of the Endogenous Latent Variables

Construct	R-square	R-square adjusted
BI	0.674	0.673
PU	0.538	0.537

Table 7 shows the R-square value of the constructs PU and BI. The R^2 value of 53.80% suggest that perceived ease of use and computer self-efficacy explain 53.80% of the variance in perceived usefulness. Similarly, the R^2 value of 67.40% reveals that 67.40% in behavioral intention is accounted for by its predictors which are perceived usefulness, computer self-efficacy, and social influence.

Table 8. Standardized Path Coefficient for Structural Model

Hypothesis	Path	β	T-value	P-value	f^2	Remarks
H_1	CS→BI	0.173	1.968	0.049	0.037	Accepted
H_2	CS→PU	0.445	5.196	0.000	0.218	Accepted
H_3	PEU→BI	0.149	1.714	0.087	0.030	Not Accepted
H_4	PEU→PU	0.349	3.922	0.000	0.134	Accepted
H_5	PU→BI	0.396	4.577	0.000	0.202	Accepted
H_6	SI→BI	0.244	2.836	0.005	0.112	Accepted

Table 8 presents the standardized path coefficients of the structural model, which indicate the strength and direction of relationships between the latent variables. The direct relationship between the latent variables; H_1 CS→BI ($\beta = 0.173$, p-value = 0.049, $f^2 = 0.037$), H_2 CS→PU ($\beta = 0.445$, p-value = 0.000, $f^2 = 0.218$), H_3 PEU→BI ($\beta = 0.149$, p-value = 0.087, $f^2 = 0.30$), H_4 PEU→PU ($\beta = 0.349$, p-value = 0.000, $f^2 = 0.134$), H_5 PU→BI ($\beta = 0.396$, p-value = 0.000, $f^2 = 0.202$), and H_6 SI→BI ($\beta = 0.244$, p-value = 0.005, $f^2 = 0.112$). Among these six hypotheses tested, five were significant (H_1, H_2, H_4, H_5 and H_6) and one insignificant (H_3).

Among the tested relationships, the strongest effect was observed for CS→PU ($\beta = 0.445$, p-value = 0.000, $f^2 = 0.218$), indicating that computer self-efficacy plays a significant role in shaping perceived usefulness, with a medium effect size. But in terms of predicting the intention to integrate AI, PU→BI ($\beta = 0.396$, p-value = 0.000, $f^2 = 0.202$) was observed to have the strongest effect, indicating that perceived usefulness is a key determinant of behavioral intention to integrate AI, with a medium effect size. On the other hand, the path from PEU→BI ($\beta = 0.149$, p-value = 0.087, $f^2 = 0.30$) was not significant, suggesting that perceived ease of use has a negligible and statistically non-significant effect on behavioral intention, which may indicate its limited relevance.

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to explore how key influencing factors, such as perceived usefulness, perceive ease of use, social influence, and computer self-efficacy, influence

teachers' behavioral intention to integrate AI in education. This study contributes to the existing body of knowledge on predictors of teachers' behavioral intention to integrate AI within the Philippines K-12 educational context. Based on the findings, the following can be drawn:

Perceived ease of use did not exhibit a significant effect on behavioral intention to integrate AI in education, as evidenced by the path coefficient ($\beta = 0.149$, p-value = 0.087). This suggests that simplicity of the features of AI tools used in education alone is insufficient to drive behavioral intention among teachers. However, perceived ease of use moderately influence perceived usefulness ($\beta = 0.349$, p-value = 0.000). This emphasizes that teachers who found AI tools easier to use were more likely to view them as beneficial in their teaching practices, highlighting the mediating effect of perceived ease of use to the relationship of perceived usefulness and behavioral intention to integrate AI. This is also confirmed by Usman et al. (2020), Arthur (2022), and Ibrahim and Shiring (2022), who highlight that teachers who perceive technology as user-friendly are more inclined to see it as beneficial.

Perceived usefulness emerged as a key determinant of BI, with the strongest predictive relationship, as indicated by the path coefficient ($\beta = 0.396$, p-value = 0.000). This result highlights the importance of teachers recognizing clear and practical benefits of AI tools in their work. Teachers who recognized the potential of AI to enhance their teaching efficiency, improve student learning outcomes, and support instructional methods were more likely to integrate AI into their practices. This is in line with the results of Zhang et al. (2023), Lu et al. (2024), and Yao and Wang (2024) which shown a strong positive relationship between perceived usefulness and teachers' intention to integrate AI.

In addition, computer self-efficacy ($\beta = 0.173$, p-value = 0.049) and social influence ($\beta = 0.244$, p-value = 0.005) significantly predicts behavioral intention to integrate AI. These emphasize that teachers are more inclined to adopt AI tools when they are confident in troubleshooting AI-related issues and learning AI integration techniques. This is similar to the studies of Li and Zhang (2024) and Du et al. (2024), which highlight the role of computer self-efficacy in AI adoption, emphasizing that higher IT proficiency and confidence in learning AI significantly increase teachers' behavioral intentions to integrate AI-generated content. However, as Alshoman (2024) pointed out, limited access to resources and insufficient professional development can hinder computer self-efficacy, reducing teachers' confidence and readiness to adopt AI in their teaching practices. Also, teacher's motivation to integrate AI are influenced by the encouragement from colleagues, school administrators, and educational trends. This is aligned with studies that emphasized that social influence plays a crucial role, with factors such as peer expectations, institutional support, and trends in educational technology driving teachers' motivation to integrate AI (Adelana et al., 2024; Gupta & Baskar, 2020; Wang et al., 2024). Collectively, these predictors provide a strong understanding of the factors shaping teachers' behavioral intentions to adopt AI in educational contexts.

Computer self-efficacy demonstrated a significant impact on perceived usefulness, as indicated by the path coefficient ($\beta = 0.445$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000$). This finding emphasizes the critical role of teachers' confidence in using technology as key factor in seeing AI tools as helpful. Similar results were found in the study of Usman et al. (2020) and Yang et al. (2024) that computer self-efficacy predicts perceived usefulness of technology.

Successful integration of AI in the Philippines' K-12 education depends on the collaborative efforts of policymakers, educational institutions, and teachers. Policymakers should strengthen frameworks that highlights the practical benefits of AI tools, such as streamlining administrative tasks and enhancing teaching, while ensuring compliance with ethical guidelines to protect data privacy of the students, teachers, and the institution. Professional development programs should prioritize hands-on training and the sharing of best practices for using AI tools, building teachers' confidence and demonstrating how these tools can effectively support their work. Educational institutions should integrate AI tools where applicable, highlighting their practical benefits in real teaching scenarios to ensure teachers recognize their value beyond theoretical ease of use.

Conclusions

This study found that perceived usefulness, computer self-efficacy, and social influence significantly influence behavioral intention to integrate AI. The findings also highlight the critical role of computer self-efficacy in shaping perceived usefulness, while perceived ease of use was found to have minimal relevance in this context. Hence, to enhance AI integration in education, policymakers, educational institutions, and stakeholders should focus on promoting the practical benefits of AI, building teacher confidence, and designing seminar and workshops that emphasize real-world applications and best practices. As AI technology continues to transform education, understanding the factors that influence teacher adoption is essential. Addressing these factors allows educational institutions to create supportive environments that foster meaningful AI integration, maximizing the potential of AI to enhance teaching and learning outcomes. As the K-12 education system in the Philippines is striving for stability, the country must proactively adopt AI-driven educational innovation to remain competitive and enhance the quality of learning. Ultimately, ensuring that both teachers and students are equipped with the necessary skills and tools to thrive in an evolving technological landscape.

Recommendations

This study was limited by its sample size and scope, focusing primarily on predictors which are perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, computer self-efficacy, and social influence. Future research should explore larger sample across Caloocan and Quezon City, as well as comparisons with other cities in the National Capital Region, to validate the findings. Additionally, examining differences and similarities in teachers' perspectives across various grade levels and specializations could provide a deeper understanding of their views on AI integration in education. Future studies should also

investigate teachers' AI reading and current practices to support the effective implementation of AI in education.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher affirms that all ethical standards were strictly observed in the conduct of this study. Informed consent was obtained from all participants after providing them with a clear explanation of the study's purpose, procedures, and their rights, including the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without any repercussions. Anonymity of the respondents was maintained by separating identifying information from the survey responses, and all data were treated with strict confidentiality. The well-being of the participants was safeguarded throughout the research process. The author declares that there is no conflict of interest in the conduct of this study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all sources and references were properly cited. The interpretation of the findings was conducted objectively, free from personal or institutional bias, and the results were used solely for academic and research purposes.

REFERENCES

- Acquah, B. Y. S., Arthur, F., Salifu, I., Quayson, E., & Nortey, S. A. (2024). Preservice teachers' behavioral intention to use artificial intelligence in lesson planning: A dual-staged PLS-SEM-ANN approach. *Computer and Education: Artificial Intelligence*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2024.100307>
- Adelana, O. P., Ayanwale, M. A., & Sanusi, I. T. (2024). Exploring pre-service biology teachers' intention to teach genetics using an AI intelligent tutoring - based system. *Cogent Education*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2024.2310976>
- Alasgarova, R., Bakhadirov, M. & Rzayev, J. (2024). Factors Influencing Teachers' Use of Artificial Intelligence for Instructional Purposes. *IAFOR Journal of Education*. 12. 9-32. 10.22492/ije.12.2.01.
- Alshorman, S. (2024). The readiness to use AI in teaching science: Science teachers' perspective. *Journal of Baltic Science Education*, 23(3), 432-448.
<https://doi.org/10.33225/jbse/24/23/432>
- Arguson, A., Maborang, M. & Paculanan, R. (2023). The Acceptability of Generative AI Tools of Selected Senior High School Teachers in Schools Divisions Office-Manila, Philippines. *Journal of Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and Neural Network*. 3. 1-10. 10.55529/jaimlnn.36.1.10.
- Arthur, Y. D. (2022). MATHEMATICS TEACHERS' ACCEPTANCE OF ICT IN TEACHING AND LEARNING: AN EXTENDED TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE MODEL. *Problems of Education in the 21st Century*, 80(3), 408-425.
- Ayanwale, M., Saunsi, I., Adelana, O., Aruleba, K. & Oyelere, S. (2022). Teachers' readiness and intention to teach artificial intelligence in schools. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*. 3. 100099. 10.1016/j.caeai.2022.100099.
- Rajapakse, C., Ariyaratna, W. & Selvakanm S. (2024). A Self-Efficacy Theory-based Study on the Teachers' Readiness to Teach Artificial Intelligence in Public Schools in Sri Lanka. *ACM Trans. Comput. Educ.* Just Accepted (September 2024).
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3691354>
- Cheung, G.W., Cooper-Thomas, H.D., Lau, R.S. et al. (2024). Reporting reliability, convergent and discriminant validity with structural equation modeling: A review and best-practice

- recommendations. *Asia Pac J Manag* 41, 745–783. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10490-023-09871-y>
- Du, H., Sun, Y., Jiang, H. et al. (2024). Exploring the effects of AI literacy in teacher learning: an empirical study. *Humanit Soc Sci Commun* 11, 559. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-024-03101-6>
- Fabella, F., & Sumandal, A. H. (2023). Teachers' Self-Efficacy with Artificial Intelligence (AI) Based Educational Tools. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 1(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.17613/7qv1-0g04>
- Giray, L., De Silos, P. Y., Adornado, A., Buelo, R. J. V., Galas, E., Reyes-Chua, E., ... Ulanday, Ma. L. (2024). Use and Impact of Artificial Intelligence in Philippine Higher Education: Reflections from Instructors and Administrators. *Internet Reference Services Quarterly*, 28(3), 315–338. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10875301.2024.2352746>
- Gupta, K. P. & Bhaskar, P. (2020). Inhibiting and motivating factors influencing teachers' adoption of AI-based teaching and learning solutions: Prioritization using analytic hierarchy process. *Journal of Information Technology Education: Research*, 19, 693-723. <https://doi.org/10.28945/4640>
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2022). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*, 3rd ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. & Sarstedt, M. (2015). A New Criterion for Assessing Discriminant Validity in Variance-based Structural Equation Modeling. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*. 43. 115-135. [10.1007/s11747-014-0403-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-014-0403-8).
- Ibrahim, A., & Shiring, E. (2022). The relationship between educators' attitudes, perceived usefulness, and perceived ease of use of instructional and web-based technologies: Implications from Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). *International Journal of Technology in Education (IJTE)*, 5(4), 535-551. <https://doi.org/10.46328/ijte.285>
- Lu, H., He, L., Yu, H., Pan, T., & Fu, K. (2024). A Study on Teachers' Willingness to Use Generative AI Technology and Its Influencing Factors: Based on an Integrated Model. *Sustainability* 2024, 16, 7216. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16167216>
- Marikyan, D. & Papagiannidis, S. (2023). Technology Acceptance Model: A review. In S. Papagiannidis (Ed), *TheoryHub Book*. Available at <https://open.ncl.ac.uk/> ISBN:9781739604400
- Li M. & Zhang, H. (2024). A Study on the Behavioral Intention of Primary and Secondary School Teachers Using Generative Artificial Intelligence in Teaching. In *Proceedings of the 2024 9th International Conference on Distance Education and Learning (ICDEL '24)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 35–41. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3675812.3675870>
- Nja, C.O., Idiege, K.J., Uwe, U.E. et al. (2023). Adoption of artificial intelligence in science teaching: From the vantage point of the African science teachers. *Smart Learn. Environ.* 10, 42. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-023-00261-x>
- Usman M.O., Septianti, A., Susita, D. & Marsofiyati, M. (2020), "The Effect of Computer Self-Efficacy and Subjective Norm on The Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use and Behavioural Intention to Use Technology", *Journal of Southeast Asian Research*, Vol. 2020 (2020), Article ID 753259, DOI: [10.5171/2020.753259](https://doi.org/10.5171/2020.753259)
- Pelaez, A., Jacobson, A., Trias, K., & Winston, E. (2022). The Turing Teacher: Identifying core attributes for AI learning in K-12. *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence*. 5, [10.3389/frai.2022.1031450](https://doi.org/10.3389/frai.2022.1031450)
- Scherer, R., & Siddiq, F. (2015). Revisiting teachers' computer self-efficacy: A differentiated view on gender differences. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 53, 48–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.06.038>
- Sevillano, S. (2024, October 26). DepEd chief optimistic on benefits of AI for quality education. *Philippine News Agency*. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1236353>

- Venkatesh, V., Morris, M. G., Davis, G. B., & Davis, F. D. (2003). User Acceptance of Information Technology: Toward a Unified View. *MIS Quarterly*, 27(3), 425–478. <https://doi.org/10.2307/30036540>
- Wang K, Ruan Q, Zhang X, Fu C, Duan B. (2024). Pre-Service Teachers' GenAI Anxiety, Technology Self-Efficacy, and TPACK: Their Structural Relations with Behavioral Intention to Design GenAI-Assisted Teaching. *Behavioral Sciences*. 14(5):373. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs14050373>
- Xiaohong, L., Jun, Z., Xiaoming, C., & Beina, Z. (2024). A study on behavioral intentions of artificial intelligence learning platform: comparing the perspectives of teachers and students. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2024.2343752>
- Yang, T., Cheon, J., & Park, E. (2024). Investigating Which Challenges Considered by Pre-service Teachers Are Reflected with Their Technology Integration Self-efficacy. *The Journal of Applied Instructional Design*: May 2024, 13(2). <https://doi.org/10.59668/1269.15648>
- Yao, N., & Wang, Q. (2024). Factors influencing pre-service special education teachers' intention toward AI in education: Digital literacy, teacher self-efficacy, perceived ease of use, and perceived usefulness. *Heliyon*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e34894>
- Zhang, C., Schießl, J., Plößl, L. et al. (2023). Acceptance of artificial intelligence among pre-service teachers: a multigroup analysis. *Int J Educ Technol High Educ* 20, 49. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-023-00420-7>
- Zhao, C. & Zhao L. (2021). Digital Nativity, Computer Self-Efficacy, and Technology Adoption: A Study Among University Faculties in China. *Front Psychol*. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.746292. PMID: 34621229; PMCID: PMC8490612.